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THE PLACE OF LANDSCAPING IN THE IMPROVEMENT OF ECONOMY

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Abstract: The article focuses on the role of landscaping services in economic development and explores the interrelationships of ecology with landscaping. It is emphasized that environmental pollution occurs concerning nature and human activities. The impact of pollution on human life is mentioned separately.

Keywords: Landscaping, Environment, Plant, Nature, Human, Anthropogenic, Pollution.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is no secret that for all developed and developing countries worldwide, beautifying urban areas and especially capitals is the focus of official authorities, political parties, social movements, the media and the general public. Along with maintaining the health of the population through the landscaping of urban and suburban areas and the planting of fruit trees, tourism will be developed, which will provide employment.

In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, it is recognized that “beautification is beautification, beautification is the addition of beauty. At the same time, prosperity, beauty, construction of landscaping, landscaping and construction works”¹ - have been used a lot.

Landscaping areas can be called green areas, including agricultural lands, landscape-recreation zones, small settlements and other facilities adjacent to large, large cities. We believe that it would be expedient to calculate the labor force and determine the indicators of development of urban subsystems, taking into account

¹Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language. O harfi. <https://ziyouz.uz/durdona-toplamlar/uzbek-tilining-izohli-lugati>(application date: 28.02.22).

the daily labor and cultural ties with the settlements around the city center, to analyze the correct and systematic implementation of landscaping.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Although Uzbekistan pays great attention to landscaping services, its activities are improved and regulated based on various normative and legal acts, it is worth noting that no research has been conducted on the development of these services. In order to effectively develop landscaping services and pay special attention to this type of service, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 10, 2013 No. 4 "On measures to improve the organization of landscaping of settlements of the Republic"decision and Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev "On additional measures to improve the efficiency of work in the field of improvement of settlements" dated June 4, No. PP-4351, according to existing cities and country district centers, In order to solve this problem, the state should take consistent measures to improve landscaping by establishing landscaping departments based on existing organizations (divisions) on landscaping in the districts and cities of the country. improvement of management, regulatory framework, standards in landscaping, and new tasks for developing and updating urban planning norms and regulations have been identified.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the implementation of the study, conclusions and recommendations were formed as a result of the analysis of indicators of effective development of landscaping services through economic methods. In addition, the methods of analysis and synthesis were effectively used in the study of landscaping by zoning.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

It is no exaggeration to say that landscaping services are one of the areas that have established themselves as a separate sector with the types of services available

today. Landscaping services are one of the areas that are in the focus of the population, along with the coverage of all developed and developing countries.

The prosperity of a country reflects not only the country's socio-economic situation but also the country's ecological situation and the socio-economic and spiritual outlook of the population in that country. Therefore, we can safely say that how the beautification service is organized determines the place of the state in political and social life.

Looking back over the past decades, we are witnessing a significant increase in the negative impact of people on the environment and especially on urban development. Year by year, the world's population growth, the growth of cities, the development of industry, all this leads to urban beautification, the problem of keeping the environment clean, the emergence of small and invisible barriers to creating adequate conditions for human life and activity. In landscaping development, it is important to consider regional factors in choosing the organizational form of management of the service system.

Urban beautification has always been the most pressing task. The word beautification can be understood in two different senses: in a narrow sense and a broad sense.

First, in the narrow sense - a house, a yard and an area that belongs only to one person or family.

Second, in a broad sense - planning, utilities, housing and land issues, sidewalks, urban green spaces, street maintenance, street transport, urban communications, urban lighting, heating, urban ecology, and pedestrian traffic congestion.

Urban development is a "mirror" that reflects the socio-economic status and level of the city, so it is no coincidence that in developed countries, information about the country's prosperity and environmental situation is open to the public and plays a leading role in political and social life.

Many plants and animals are disappearing from the face of the earth due to human misconduct. The worldview shaped over millions of years has changed thanks to man dramatically. Humanity has always used the environment primarily as a source of resources.

Environmental pollution occurs concerning nature and human activities. Suppose we understand the main sources of natural pollution: natural processes such as volcanoes, earthquakes, floods, landslides, floods, strong winds, and fires. Pollution resulting from human activities is called anthropogenic pollution.

On the natural component of anthropogenic pollution: water pollution, air, soil landscape pollution.

According to the duration of anthropogenic pollution: temporary and permanent;

According to the scale of distribution: are divided into planetary, regional (territorial or regional) and local (local) groups.

In terms of type and sources of pollution: divided into physical, chemical, biological, mechanical and other types.

Physical pollution- heat, light, electromagnetic, radioactive, vibrations.

Noise harms human health, especially the nervous system and hearing. As a result, a person becomes tired quickly, mental ability decreases, various heart and nerve diseases.

Infrasound (inaudible sounds) also has a negative impact on human health. In humans, this sound creates a feeling of fear. In electromagnetic pollution, the average wavelength is from 10-14 to 14 m.

Biological pollution- Viruses and microbes that spread in the air, water and soil cause disease in humans and animals.

Mechanical pollution is any non-perishable waste. On the surface, the oceans are filling up with this waste.

It is becoming increasingly clear that anthropogenic pollution is causing various environmental problems, sometimes extremely dangerous to human life. One of the most acute problems is the planetary problem, the peculiarity of which is that it applies to all people on Earth. Some man-made waste accumulates in the air, some in the oceans, and nothing disappears without a trace. Because of this, the search for ways to eliminate them and their immediate implementation is one of the key issues facing all countries.

V. CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, we believe that it would be expedient to strengthen further the social partnership of non-governmental and non-profit organizations with local government agencies in solving landscaping problems, especially in the field, and to make better use of our domestic potential in the development of landscaping services. For this, we believe that each of us should first all pay attention to the prosperity of our homes, streets, workplaces, as well as our cities, waste is placed in separate bins⁷⁶. If we can fulfill the above tasks, we will make a significant contribution to our economy.

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